

Constituents of *Zizyphus jujuba*

M. B. Pandey^a, J. P. Singh^a, Sarita Singh^b and A. K. Singh^{b*}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, S.G.R. Post Graduate College, Dobhi-222 149, Uttar Pradesh, India
(Purvanchal University, Jaunpur, Uttar Pradesh, India)

^bDepartment of Medicinal Chemistry, Institute of Medical Sciences, Banaras Hindu University,
Varanasi-221 005, Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail : singhak06@rediffmail.com Fax : 91-542-2367568

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Abstract : Three flavonoids, kaempferol-7-methylether, kaempferol and myrecetin together with a cyclopeptide alkaloid, nummularine-K have been isolated from the barks of *Zizyphus jujuba* and their structures established by spectral evidences. This is the first report of occurrence of these compounds in *Z. jujuba*.

Keywords : Medicinal plants, flavonoids, cyclopeptide alkaloid.

Introduction

Zizyphus jujuba Mill. (Rhamnaceae) is distributed in Punjab, Himalaya upto 6500 ft, Bengal and N.W. Provinces. In Indian system of medicine, the bark is used to heal ulcers and wounds, gum in eye diseases, leaves in scabies and throat troubles, fruits in chronic bronchitis, fever and liver diseases and seeds in dry cough and skin diseases^{1,2}. Here we report the isolation of three flavonoids and a cyclopeptide alkaloid from the barks of *Z. jujuba* which have not earlier been reported from this plant.

Experimental

Dried barks (4.5 kg) were powdered and repeatedly extracted with a mixture of C₆H₆-NH₄OH-MeOH (100 : 1 : 1). The total extract was concentrated under reduced pressure and extracted with 7% aqueous citric acid. The acidic solution was basified with ammonia and extracted with CHCl₃ which furnished the crude base fraction. The crude base fraction was chromatographed over SiO₂ gel column eluting with a mixture of CHCl₃ and MeOH. The eluents collected from CHCl₃ followed by preparative TLC with solvents CHCl₃-MeOH (20 : 1) and CHCl₃-MeOH (10 : 1) and crystallisation from MeOH furnished the alkaloid nummularine-K^{3,4} (21 mg) (1) as colourless granules, m.p. 235–238 °C.

Dried powdered barks (2.5 kg) were further extracted with MeOH in a Soxhlet extractor which on removal of solvent gave a brown gummy mass (105 g). The MeOH

extract was chromatographed over SiO₂ gel column. The eluents collected from CHCl₃, CHCl₃-MeOH (10 : 1) and CHCl₃-MeOH (9 : 1) on crystallisation from MeOH furnished kaempferol-7-methylether⁵ (30 mg) (2) as yellow granules, m.p. 218–221 °C, kaempferol (20 mg) (3) as yellow granules, m.p. 270–272 °C and myrecetin⁵ (25 mg) (4) as yellow granules, m.p. 350–353 °C.

Nummularine-K (1) : It exhibited UV λ_{\max} (MeOH) nm : 223 (strong end absorption), 290sh, 281, 273; $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ -43° (c, 0.06, MeOH); IR ν_{\max} (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3270 (-NH), 2980–2830 (-CH), 2785 (-NCH₃), 1675 and 1635 (sec. amide), 1610 (-C=C-), 1230 and 980 (phenol ether); HRMS, *m/z* : 573.3324 ([M]⁺, C₃₃H₄₃N₅O₅), 443.2654 (C₂₄H₃₅N₄O₄), 387, 303.2069 (C₁₈H₂₇N₂O₂), 274, 195, 190.1237 (C₁₂H₁₆NO), 187.1237 (C₁₂H₁₅N₂, base peak), 182, 167, 135.0683 (C₈H₉NO), 130.0655 (C₉H₈N), 97.0655 (C₉H₉O), 86.0976 (C₅H₁₂N). Hydrolysis of the compound 1 with 6 N HCl in a sealed tube for 20 h at 120 °C furnished two ninhydrin positive spots in the hydrolysate identified as 3-hydroxyleucine and leucine by PC comparison with authentic samples. The compound 1 was further hydrolysed with Ba(OH)₂ for 24 h at 120 °C which furnished one Ehrlich's reagent positive spot in the hydrolysate identified as *N,N*-dimethyltryptophan by co-PC with authentic sample.

Kaempferol-7-methylether (2) : It exhibited UV λ_{\max} (MeOH) nm : 253, 266, 320, 363; IR ν_{\max} (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3150–3350 (-OH), 1660 (conjugated carbonyl); 90 MHz

^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ : 3.70 (3H, s), 6.11 (1H, d, J 2 Hz), 6.46 (1H, d, J 2 Hz), 6.67 (1H, d, J 8 Hz), 7.74 (1H, d, J 8 Hz), 9.11 (1H, s, -OH), 9.70 (1H, s, -OH), 11.98 (1H, s, -OH); MS, m/z : 300 ($[\text{M}]^+$), 272, 258, 257, 243, 229, 213, 181, 176, 169, 138, 124, 121, 119, 69 (Found: C, 63.7; H, 3.98. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_6$: C, 64.0; H, 4.0%).

Kaempferol (3): It exhibited UV λ_{max} (MeOH) nm: 254sh, 266, 294sh, 322sh, 367; IR ν_{max} (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3000–3500 (-OH), 1650, 1600 (conjugated carbonyl); 90 MHz ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ : 6.18 (1H, d, J 2 Hz), 6.45 (1H, d, J 2 Hz), 6.95 (2H, d, J 9 Hz), 8.00 (2H, d, J 9 Hz), 10.80 (1H, br s, -OH), 12.50 (1H, br s, -OH); MS, m/z : 286 ($[\text{M}]^+$), 284, 258, 229, 213, 153, 143, 129, 121.

Myricetin (4): It exhibited UV λ_{max} (MeOH) nm: 254, 272sh, 301sh, 374; IR ν_{max} (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3100–3500 (-OH), 1660 and 1600 (conjugated carbonyl); 90 MHz ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ : 6.02 (1H, d, J 2 Hz), 6.22 (1H, d, J 2 Hz), 7.28 (2H, br s), 9.30 (-OH), 10.62 (br s, -OH), 12.33 (br s, -OH); MS, m/z : 318 ($[\text{M}]^+$), 302, 290, 289, 286, 261, 244, 166, 153, 146, 124, 108, 79, 69.

The structures of all the above compounds were confirmed by direct comparison with authentic samples (m.m.p., co-TLC and superimposable IR).

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